

At 20 locations selected to represent different climatic conditions, cultivation techniques, varieties, and soil types, 6-12 ricefields were sampled at nine spots—the four corners, midway along each edge, and at the center—and disease incidence or severity recorded.

Leaf and neck blast (Bl) caused by *Pyricularia oryzae*, leaf scald (LSc) caused by *Rhynchosporium oryzae*, and brown spot (BS) caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* occurred everywhere, although severity was low in the Extreme North Province (Table 2). These diseases are thought to cause significant losses in yield, particularly at Mbo Plain in the West Province and at Karewa and Laqdo area in the North Province.

Disease was most severe under upland conditions, especially at Mbo Plain in the West Province. Irrigated fields suffered more severe disease incidence in the dry season crop, which coincides with low temperatures.

Sheath rot (ShR) caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae* Saw. and glume discoloration (GID) caused by several pathogenic fungi, including *Cochliobolus miyabeanus* were serious at Ndop Plain in the North West Province. The relatively high incidence of these diseases at Ndop Plain in the wet season and elsewhere in the dry season was probably due to low temperatures, which predisposed the crop to the fungi. ShR and GID are believed to cause some direct yield losses, especially at Ndop Plain, because infected panicles fail to fully exsert.

Table 1. Rice production in different rice-growing areas of Cameroon.

Ecology and province	Area ($\times 10^2$ ha)		Production ($\times 10^2$ t)	
	1981-82	1986-87	1981-82	1986-87
Irrigated rice				
Extreme North	172	105 (87) ^a	416	780
North	-	40	-	86
North West	26	34	58	104
West	10	10	10	20
Upland rice	7	10	14	24

^aDouble-cropped areas

Table 2. Distribution and severity of diseases in the major rice-growing areas^a in Cameroon.

Disease	Disease severity ^b					
	Extreme North (300 m), irrigated	North (200 m), irrigated	North West (1200 m)		West (600 m)	
			Irrigated	Upland	Irrigated	Upland
Leaf blast	1	3/5	3	3/5	3/5	3/5
Neck blast	1	3/5	3	3/5	3/5	3/5
Sheath rot	1	3	5	5	3	3
Glume discoloration	1	3	5	5	3	3
Leaf scald	0	3	3	5	5	5/7
Brown spot	0	3	3	5	3	3
Bacterial blight	3	0	0	0	0	0

^aNumbers in parentheses indicate altitude. ^bBy the *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale 1-9.

Bacterial blight (BB) caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* was only found in the Extreme North Province, on test varieties in experimental fields at Yagoua and Maga. IR46 is the only recommended variety grown on about 11,000 ha of irrigated fields in the Extreme North; it was found to be resistant to BB. Most recommended and promising rice varieties with better qualities than IR46 are susceptible.

In general, disease incidence or severity varied among the different rice-growing areas. The relatively low occurrence of diseases in the Northern

Provinces may be due to several factors. High soil fertility results in healthy and vigorous plants better able to resist invasions by disease pathogens. Low humidity and higher wind velocities may prevent water droplets from being retained on leaf surfaces long enough to facilitate spore germination.

In the Western Highlands, the climate is more conducive to disease establishment. Mbo Plain in the West Province was found to be suitable for screening for rice Bl, LSc. and BS; Ndop plain in the North West. for ShR and GID. ■

Collar rot of rice in Manipur

N. I. Singh and R. K. T. Devi, *Botany and Plant Pathology Department, Manipur Agricultural College, Iroisemba, Imphal 795001, India*

Rice varieties China and Akhanphou, and some new breeding lines of rice in experimental fields were affected by collar rot disease during 1989 wet season.

The disease appeared as small brown lesions at the collar joining the leaf blade and leaf sheath. As the disease advanced, lesions increased in size, turned dark brown, and caused rot (see figure).

Rice collar rot caused by *Ascochyta oryzae* Catt.

Eventually, the affected leaf blade withered and dropped off.

The causal organism was isolated on potato dextrose agar. A pathogenicity test was performed by placing a drop of mycelial fragment prepared from 7-d-old culture at the collar region during

the late booting stage. Affected collar regions were collected and placed in sterile petri dishes lined with moist filter paper.

The fungus produced numerous pycnidia on the affected tissue. Pycnidia were dark, separated, immersed in host

tissue, and ostiolate. Conidia were hyaline, oblong, rounded at both ends, 14-15 × 4 µm.

The causal fungus was identified as *Ascochyta oryzae* Catt. This is the first record of its occurrence in Manipur. ■

Effect of some leguminous crops on number and viability of *Sclerotium oryzae* sclerotia

S. Hussain, Pulses Programme, National Agricultural Research Centre, Islamabad 45500; and A. Ghaffar, Botany Department University of Karachi, Karachi, Pakistan

In the crop rotation pattern of Pakistan, rice usually follows wheat. Leguminous crops which have the ability to restore soil fertility by fixing N from atmosphere also are planted as dry season crops.

We studied the effect on rice of growing a leguminous crop in soil infested with sclerotia of *S. oryzae* (the cause of stem rot in rice). Wheat was planted as a control. The experiment was laid out in a complete block design with four replications.

Berseem (*Trifolium alexandrinum*) gram (*Cicer arietinum*), lentil (*Lens*

Table 1. Effect of leguminous crops on number and viability of *Sclerotium oryzae* sclerotia. ^a Sheikhpura, Pakistan.

Crop rotation ^b	1986 wet season		1986-87 dry season		1987 wet season	
	Population	Viability (%)	Population	Viability (%)	Population	Viability (%)
R-W-R	9 a	63 a	8 a	70 a	8 a	87 a
R-L-R	8 a	60 a	10 a	78 a	7 a	74 a
R-G-R	9 a	52 a	10 a	64 a	13 a	83 a
R-B-R	14 b	73 a	8 a	41 b	6 a	89 a

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at P < 0.05 by Duncan's Multiple Range Test. ^b R = rice, W = wheat, L = lentil, G = gram, B = berseem.

culinaris), and wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) were planted in Nov and harvested in Apr. Rice (*Oryza sativa*) was transplanted in Jun and harvested in Oct. Recommended NPK was applied. Sclerotia were separated from soil by sieving and flotation technique after harvest of each crop. Their viability was tested on water agar supplemented with streptomycin sulfate and penicillin at 3,000 ppm each.

Population and viability were reduced up to 43% after berseem; there were no significant reductions in sclerotia after

Table 2. Effect of a leguminous crop on rice yield. Sheikhpura, Pakistan.

Crop rotation	Rice yield ^a (t/ha)	Yield Increase (%)
Wheat - rice	5.1 c	-
Lentil - rice	5.2 bc	3
Gram - rice	6.0 b	17
Berseem - rice	6.9 a	35

^a Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at P < 0.05 by Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

rice (Table 1). Rice yields increased significantly when berseem was used in the rotation (Table 2). ■

Etiology of grain discoloration in upland rice in West Sumatra

J. Castano, K. Klap, and Z. Zaini, Sukarami Research Institute for Food Crops, P.O. Box 34, Padang 25001, West Sumatra, Indonesia

Rice grain discoloration is becoming a serious problem in tropical rice production areas, particularly in upland rice. In Indonesia, it is common to find the disease in upland rice grown in acid soils, such as the red-yellow Podzolic soils of West Sumatra.

We collected seeds of susceptible upland rice cultivar Tondano and panicles of local upland rice cultivars Arias and Simariti showing different levels of disease severity. The seeds were seeded after the agar plate test and incubated in a

Microorganisms associated with grain discoloration levels (1, 10, 30, 60, 100%) in upland rice. West Sumatra, Indonesia.

Microorganism	Microorganisms (%) at indicated level of grain discoloration				
	1%	10%	30%	60%	100%
<i>Helminthosporium oryzae</i>	14 ^a	17	22	41	40
<i>Trichoconis padwickii</i>	50	30	14	5	7
<i>Phoma</i> sp.	12	34	24	30	2
<i>Nigrospora</i> sp.	12	8	13	8	7
<i>Curvularia</i> sp.	9	7	15	7	8
<i>Torula</i> sp.	3	1	1	3	9
<i>Mycovellosiella oryzae</i>	1	4	0	3	0
<i>Cercospora janseana</i>	2	2	0	1	0
<i>Phyllosticta</i> sp.	0	2	1	2	0
<i>Chaetomium</i> sp.	0	0	0	5	0
<i>Gerlachia oryzae</i>	1	0	2	0	0
<i>Phomopsis</i> sp.	0	2	0	1	0
<i>Cercospora oryzae</i>	0	0	1	2	0
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	2	0	0	0	1
<i>Gonatobotrys</i> sp.	1	0	0	0	0
<i>Macrophoma</i> sp.	0	1	0	0	0
<i>Memnoniella</i> sp.	0	1	0	0	0
<i>Helicoceras oryzae</i>	0	0	1	0	0
<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	0	0	0	0	1
<i>Diplodia oryzae</i>	0	0	0	0	1

^a Data from 100 seeds.